

Late Paleozoic Evolution of the Anadarko Basin: Implications for Laurentian Tectonics and the Assembly of Pangea: Supporting Information

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List of contents:

Table 1 (Details and source of data used to construct figure 5)

Plates A-E (Location of data used to construct figure 5)

Plate F (Uninterpreted seismic line OK483_120EXT)

Plate G (Uninterpreted seismic line OK432_05)

Plate H (Uninterpreted seismic line OK526_133)

Table 1

The table in the following pages contains information on the data sources for the thickness maps in figure 5 of the paper..Georeferenced outlines of the studies are shown in appendix plates A through E. The number in the first column of table 1 corresponds to the outline number in the appendix plate. The letter in the second column denotes the plate in which the outline of the publication study area is shown. Column three indicates the author; column four indicates the formation identified by each author; and column five shows what time slice the formation in column four is associated to for the compilation of the thickness maps. Column six indicates the data type that was used and column seven indicates the data quality. References can be found in main paper.

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
1	A	Turko, 2019	Springer c. base (Black Marker, i.e., base Goddard); Springer top (Woods SS)	Mississippian/Springerian (Early Pennsylvanian)	depths taken from seismic lines, faults	High
			Dornick Hills (Lower Dornick Hills top (?))	Morrowan top		
			Dornick Hills (Upper Dornick Hills)	Atokan top		
			Hoxbar base (County Line LS)	Missourian base		
			Cisco top	Pennsylvanian top		
2	A	Kumar and Slatt, 1984	Middle Tonkawa SS	Missourian top	Structure map	Low
3	A	Dutton et al., 1979	Structure map of top precambrian basement	Faults	Faults and modifying final Mississippian thickness map	Medium-low
			Mississippian Isopach	Mississippian thickness		
4	A	Huffman, 1959	Mississippian system	Mississippian thickness	Modify final thickness map	Low
			Morrow series	Morrowan thickness		
			Atoka series	Atokan thickness		
5	A	Jones Jr, 1961	Morrowan series	Morrowan thickness	Structure map and modify final thickness map	Medium-low
			Atokan series	Atokan thickness		
			Contour mississippian units	Mississippian top structure		
6	A	Reed, 1959	Goddard Fm.	Mississippian depth and thickness	Geologic cross section for depth and thickness Structure map	Medium
			Pre-Atokan unconformity	Atoka base		

Table 1 continued

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
7	A	George, 2016	Cisco-Canyon	Base Missourian depth and top Virgilian depth	Interpreted seismic line	High
			Strawn Group	Desmoinesian thickness and depth		
			Bend-Caddo	Atokan thickness and depth		
			Marble Falls Limestone	Morrowan thickness and depth		
			Barnett shale	Mississippian depth and thickness		
8	B	Gilbert, 1982	NA	NA	Surface data and faults	Medium-low
9	B	Galloway et al., 1977	NA	Missourian platform margin		Low
10	B	LoCricchio, 2014	GWJ,QWI,GWH,GWG,SKINNER,GWF,GWE,GWD,GWC,GWB, BRITT	Desmoinesian thickness	Modify final thickness map	Medium-low
11 & 28	B & D	Clement, 1991	Morrow top	Morrowan top	Structure map	Low
12	B	Jacobsen, 1949	Deese group	Desmoinesian thickness	Isopach maps and Cross sections	Medium-low
			Dornick Hills	Atokan thickness		
			Springer SH	Mississippian thickness		
13	B	Jacobson, 1984	Base of Pennsylvanian	Morrowan base	Structure map; thickness and depth from cross sections	Medium-low
			Morrow	Morrowan thickness and depth		
			Atoka	Atokan thickness and depth		
			Deese	Desmoinesian thickness and depth		
			Hoxbar	Missourian thickness and depth		
			Cisco	Virgilian thickness and depth		

Table 1 continued

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
14 & 17	B & C	Lyday, 1985	Atoka	Atoka top	Structure map	Medium
			Morrowan, Atokan, Desmoinesian, Missourian, Virgilian	Morrowan, Atokan, Desmoinesian, Missourian, Virgilian	Depth and thickness from cross section	Low
15	B	Abels, 1959	Morrow top	Morrowan top	Structure map	Medium
16	C	Davis and Northcutt, 1989	Hougaton top (Top Chase unit/ base Council grove)	Contour of structure map Virgilian top (?)	Structure map	Low
18	C	Tarr et al., 1965	NA	NA	Surface geology	High
19	C	Shelby, 1980	Mississippian, Morrow, Atoka	Morrowan thickness	Geologic cross section	Low
20	C	Carpenter and Tapp, 2014	NA	NA	Faults from structure map	High
21	C	Ham et al., 1954	NA	Used for edges of formations in the Arbuckle Uplift and to trace major faults	Surface data, faults	High
22	D	Blome et al., 2013	Springer Formation	Mississippian/Springerian (Early Pennsylvanian) top and base	Depths taken from cross section, surface data, faults	Medium
			Deese Group	Desmoinesian top and base		
23	D	Donovan, 1982	NA	NA	Faults	High
24	D	Herrmann, 1961	Hoxbar	Missourian top	Depths from well based structural cross sections, structure and thickness maps	Medium
			Deese	Desmoinesian top		
			Atoka	Atokan top		
			Morrow	Morrowan top		
25	D	Burak, 2016	Marmaton top	Desmoinesian top	Structure map	High

Table 1 continued

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
26	D	Axtmann, 1985	Sylvan structure map	Faults	Faults	Medium
27	D	Beach, 1989	Viola Springs formation structural contour map	Faults	Faults	Medium-high
			Deese group	Desmoinesian thickness	Unit depth and thickness from cross section	
			Hoxbar group	Missourian thickness		
29	D	Hayes, 1955	Cisco group	Virgilian thickness and depth	Thickness and depth from cross sections	Medium-low
			Hoxbar group	Missourian depth and thickness		
			Deese Fm	Desmoinesian thickness		
30	D	Markas, 1967	2nd Checkrboard LM	Desmoinesian top	Thicknesses fomr cross sections	Medium-low
			Dornick hills	Atokan top		
			Springer - Goddard	Mississippian top		
31	D	Pate, 1955	Top Woods SS	Mississippian top structure map	Structure map and cross sections for unit depths and thicknesses	Medium
			Todd sd.	Missourian base cross section		
			Cisco	Virgiliand on cross section		
32	D	Westheimer, 1965	Base Deese Group	Depth base Desmoinesian	Geologic cross section, faults from geologic map	Medium-low
			Goddard Fm.	Depth and thickness of Mississippian		
33	D	Brown, 1984	Springer	Mississippian thickness and depth	Thickness and depth form geologic cross sections, faults form structure maps	Low
			Atoka	Atokan thickness and depth		
			Deese	Desmoinesian thickness and depth		
34	D	Kilic and Tapp, 2013	Springer	Mississippian base	Depth from cross section and faults from structure map	High

Table 1 continued

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
35	D	Read and Richmond, 1993	Deese	Desmoinesian	Thickness and depth from geologic cross sections	Low
			Hoxbar	Missourian		
			Cisco	Virgilian		
36	D	Harlton, 1956	Top Deese Formation	Desmoinesian top	Contour maps and geologic cross sections	Medium
			Top Lake Murray	Atokan top		
37	D	Jemison Jr, 1978	NA	NA	Faults from structure map	Medium-low
38	E	Harlton, 1964	Goddard-Springer	Mississippian	Thickness and depth from geologic cross sections, faults from structure maps	Low
			Deese	Desmoinesian		
39	E	Karis, 2015	Marmaton top	Desmoinesian top	Structure map	High
40	E	Wallace, 1953	Top of Deese Formation	Desmoinesian top	Structure map	Medium
			Top of Primrose Sandstone	Mississippian top	Structure map	
41	E	Haas, 1978	Reagan fault zone map	NA	Faults	Medium
42	E	Rutledge, 1956	NA	NA	Faults from structure map	Medium-low
NA	Entire study area	Cooper, 1995	Springer-Goddard	Mississippian	Thickness and depth from cross sections	Medium-high
			Morrowan	Morrowan		
			Dornik Hills	Atokan		
			Deese	Desmoinesian		
			Hoxbar	Missourian		
NA	Entire study area	Saxon, 1998	Morrowan, Atokan, Desmoinesian, Missourian, Virgilian	Morrowan, Atokan, Desmoinesian, Missourian, Virgilian	Thickness and depth from cross sections	Medium

Table 1 continued

Number	Plate	Author	Formations identified by author	Corresponding surface in this paper	Data used	Data quality
NA	Entire study area	McKee and Crosby, 1975	Interval A	Morrowan	Thickness maps	Low
			Interval B	Atokan		
			Interval C	Desmoinesian		
			Interval D	Missourian		
			Interval E	Virgilian		
NA	Entire study area	Marsh and Holland 2016	NA	NA	USGS fault database	High
NA	Anadarko Basin	Higley et al., 2014	Base of Pennsylvanian	Morrowan base	Structure map	High
			Morrow	Morrowan thickness and depth		
			Atoka	Atokan thickness and depth		
			Deese	Desmoinesian thickness and depth		
			Hoxbar	Missourian thickness and depth		
			Cisco	Virgilian thickness and depth		
NA	Fort Worth Basin	Alsalem et al., 2017	Barnett shale	Mississippian depth and thickness	Thickness maps	Medium
			Marble Falls Formation	Morrowan thickness and depth		
			upper Bend Group	Atokan thickness and depth		
			Strawn Group	Desmoinesian thickness and depth		

100°0'0"W

98°0'0"W

37

25

28

30

24

26

23

29

31

34

33

22

36

35

27

32

N

0 12.5 25 50 75 100 Kilometers

Plate D

100°0'0"W

98°0'0"W

34°0'0"N

34°0'0"N

SW

Plate G

NE

Trace No.

150

200

250

300

350

400

C

OK432_85

TWT (s)

1

2

3

4

0

2.5

5

7.5

10 km

Line OK483_120EXT

